

The Impact of Probiotics Treatment in the Therapy of Ulcerative Colitis in Najaf City

Shymaa Nema Hamed Alsaltani

Iraqi Ministry of Health, Al-Najaf Teaching Hospital. Al-Najaf, Iraq

Zahraa Hussam Eldin Ismaeel

Consultant in Family Medicine, Ghazi Al-Hariri Teaching Hospital, Baghdad Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq

Seveem Omran Jasim

Baghdad Medical City Hospital, Baghdad, Iraq

Samer Nema Yassen Alkewawy

College of Medicine, University of Kufa, Al-Najaf, Iraq

Abstract

Background: Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a chronic inflammatory bowel disease marked by relapsing colonic inflammation and impaired quality of life. Emerging evidence suggests that gut microbiota play a key role in disease pathogenesis, and probiotics may offer therapeutic benefits by restoring microbial balance. **Objective:** This study aimed to evaluate the clinical impact of oral probiotic supplementation in patients with mild to moderate UC in Najaf City. **Methods:** A single-blind, randomized clinical trial was conducted involving 87 adult UC patients. Participants were randomly allocated into two groups: the intervention group received a daily oral probiotic supplement (25×10^9 CFU of 10 strains) alongside standard UC therapy, while the control group received a placebo with the same standard treatment. The treatment duration was 8 weeks. Clinical effectiveness was assessed using the Mayo Disease Activity Index (MDAI), and changes were evaluated before and after treatment. **Results:** Baseline demographic and clinical features were comparable between the two groups except for gender distribution. After 8 weeks, the probiotics group showed significantly better outcomes: higher rates of clinical remission ($P = 0.009$), more cases shifting to mild disease, and fewer cases remaining moderate compared to placebo. Within the probiotics group, there was a significant reduction in rectal bleeding, stool frequency, physician global assessment (PGA), and mucosal scores ($P < 0.0001$). Between-group comparison post-treatment also showed superior outcomes in the probiotics group across most parameters. **Conclusion:** Probiotic therapy significantly improved clinical symptoms and disease activity in UC patients, supporting its role as a safe and effective adjunct to standard treatment.

Introduction

Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a chronic inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) characterized by relapsing and remitting inflammation of the colonic mucosa, predominantly affecting the rectum and extending proximally in a continuous manner. The exact etiology of UC remains unknown; however, it is widely believed to result from a complex interplay between genetic predisposition, immune system dysregulation, environmental factors, and alterations in the gut microbiota [1,2]. The clinical presentation of UC includes symptoms such as

abdominal pain, bloody diarrhea, urgency, and weight loss, significantly impairing patients' quality of life [3]. Conventional treatment of UC primarily relies on the use of anti-inflammatory drugs such as aminosalicylates, corticosteroids, immunosuppressants, and biologics targeting specific immune pathways. While these agents are effective in inducing and maintaining remission, many patients experience adverse effects or incomplete responses, necessitating the exploration of complementary therapeutic options [4,5]. In recent years, increasing

More Information

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attention has been directed toward the role of the gut microbiome in the pathogenesis and progression of UC. Dysbiosis—an imbalance in the composition and function of gut microbiota—has been consistently observed in UC patients, marked by reduced microbial diversity and decreased abundance of beneficial bacteria such as *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* [6,7]. Probiotics, defined as live microorganisms that confer a health benefit when administered in adequate amounts, have emerged as a promising adjunctive therapy for UC by aiming to restore microbial balance, enhance mucosal barrier function, and modulate immune responses [8]. Several randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses have shown that certain probiotic strains, particularly *Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917, *VSL#3*, and *Bifidobacterium* species, may be effective in inducing and maintaining remission in UC, with efficacy comparable to conventional treatments in some cases [9,10]. The mechanisms through which probiotics exert their beneficial effects include competitive inhibition of pathogenic bacteria, production of anti-inflammatory metabolites such as short-chain fatty acids, strengthening of epithelial tight junctions, and downregulation of proinflammatory cytokines [11]. Moreover, probiotics may contribute to immune tolerance by enhancing regulatory T cell responses and modulating dendritic cell function, thus attenuating the exaggerated mucosal immune activation characteristic of UC [12]. Aims of the study: To evaluate the impact of probiotics oral supplement on patients with mild to moderate ulcerative colitis in Najaf city.

Method

This single-blind, randomized clinical trial was conducted in Najaf City to estimate the impact of probiotic therapy on patients with mild to moderate ulcerative colitis (UC) with Mayo Disease Activity Index (MDAI) score 3-9. A total of 87 patients, aged above 18 years and previously diagnosed with UC based on clinical, endoscopic, and histological criteria, were recruited from gastroenterology clinics in Gastroenterology and Hepatology hospital in Najaf city. The study received ethical approval, and informed

consent was obtained from all participants before enrollment. Participants were randomly assigned into two groups. The intervention group received a daily oral probiotic tablet containing viable strains of bacteria and ulcerative colitis therapy. The control group received a placebo tablet identical in appearance and dosage schedule, alongside the same standard therapy. The duration of treatment for both groups was 8 weeks. The clinical efficacy of treatment was assessed using the Mayo Disease Activity Index (MDAI), a validated tool comprising four subscores: stool frequency, rectal bleeding, endoscopic findings, and physician’s global assessment [13]. Each parameter is scored from 0 to 3, with higher scores indicating greater disease activity. Baseline MDAI scores were recorded before treatment initiation, and follow-up assessments were conducted at the end of the 8-week period. To minimize bias, patients were blinded to their group allocation, though the clinicians were aware of the treatment assignments. Clinical evaluations included symptom monitoring, physical examination, and follow-up colonoscopy. the rate of clinical remission, defined as a total MDAI score ≤2. Data were analyzed using SPSS software. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation, and categorical variables as percentages. Statistical significance was set at *P* < 0.05.

Results

comparing the placebo and probiotics groups based on age, gender, and disease extent showed in table 1. According to Age Group: No significant difference was found between the two groups (<30 years vs. ≥30 years; *P* = 0.5), indicating similar age distribution. Regarding to Gender: A statistically significant difference was observed (*P* = 0.03), with more females in the placebo group (55.8%) and more males in the probiotics group (68.6%). Extent of Colitis: There were no significant differences in disease extent (left-sided colitis, pancolitis, proctocolitis) between groups (*P* = 0.7), showing both groups had comparable disease distribution. So except for gender, baseline characteristics between the placebo and probiotics groups were statistically similar.

Table 1: Association between Placebo and Probiotics Group According (Age Group, Gender, Extent and Duration)

Age Group (years)	Groups		P-value
	Placebo (No. %)	Probiotics (No. %)	
<30	30 (57.7%)	17 (48.6%)	0.5
≥30	22 (42.3%)	18 (51.4%)	
Gender	Placebo (No. %)	Probiotics (No. %)	P-value
Female	29 (55.8%)	11 (31.4%)	0.03
Male	23 (44.2%)	24 (68.6%)	
Extent	Placebo (No. %)	Probiotics (No. %)	P-value
Left sided colitis	28 (53.8%)	16 (45.7%)	0.7
Pan colitis	4 (7.7%)	3 (8.6%)	
Proctocolitis	20 (38.5%)	2 (45.7%)	

Before treatment, there was no significant difference in disease severity between the placebo and probiotics groups ($P = 0.3$); most patients in both groups had moderate UC. After treatment, the probiotics group

showed significantly better outcomes ($P = 0.009$), with: More patients achieving mild disease (62.9% vs. 51.9%), Fewer with moderate disease (11.4% vs. 38.5%), Higher remission rate (25.7% vs. 9.6%). As in table 2.

Table 2: Association between Placebo and Probiotics Group According to UC Score Before and After

	Groups		
UC Score (Before)	Placebo (No. %)	Probiotics (No. %)	P-value
Mild	22 (42.3%)	10 (28.6%)	0.3
Moderate	30 (57.7%)	25 (71.4%)	
UC Score (After)	Placebo (No. %)	Probiotics (No. %)	P-value
Mild	27 (51.9%)	22 (62.9%)	0.009
Moderate	20 (38.5%)	4 (11.4%)	
Remission	5 (9.6%)	3 (25.7%)	

Evaluates within-group changes in the probiotics group before and after treatment, using mean scores for clinical parameters. All four parameters—rectal bleeding, stool frequency, PGA (Physician Global Assessment), and mucosal findings—showed statistically significant improvement ($P = 0.0001$ for all).

Mean scores decreased notably after treatment, e.g., rectal bleeding dropped from 1.543 to 0.714, and mucosal findings from 1.514 to 0.971. Probiotics significantly improved all clinical and mucosal indicators in patients after treatment. As in table 3.

Table 3: Differences Mean of Scores in Patients Received Probiotics only (Before and After Received)

Parameter (Score)	Before (Mean ± SD)	After (Mean ± SD)	P-value
Rectal Bleeding	1.543 ± 0.78	0.714 ± 0.52	0.0001
Stool Frequency	1.657 ± 0.54	1.029 ± 0.62	0.0001
PGA	1.571 ± 0.74	0.886 ± 0.58	0.0001
Mucosal Finding	1.514 ± 0.51	0.971 ± 0.57	0.0001

Table 4 compares mean scores after treatment between the placebo and probiotics groups. Rectal bleeding, stool frequency, and PGA scores were significantly lower in the probiotics group compared to placebo ($P < 0.05$), indicating better clinical outcomes. Although mucosal findings were also lower in the

probiotics group (0.971 vs. 1.192), the difference was not statistically significant ($P = 0.09$). After treatment, probiotics outperformed placebo in reducing clinical symptoms, with borderline improvement in mucosal findings.

Table 4: Differences Mean of Scores in Patients Received Placebo and Probiotics Group (After Received)

Parameter (After)	Placebo (Mean ± SE)	Probiotics (Mean ± SE)	P-value
Rectal Bleeding	1.212 ± 0.0839	0.714 ± 0.0877	0.0001
Stool Frequency	1.327 ± 0.0979	1.029 ± 0.1044	0.04
PGA	1.212 ± 0.0925	0.886 ± 0.0985	0.01
Mucosal Finding	1.192 ± 0.087	0.971 ± 0.096	0.09

Discussion

Collectively, our study supports the adjunctive role of probiotics in managing mild to moderate ulcerative colitis. Probiotics led to significant symptom relief and improved disease scores, with trends toward better mucosal healing. The results align closely with recent global studies, confirming the reliability of probiotic therapy as a safe, effective supplement to standard UC treatments. Future trials with larger populations and longer follow-up are warranted to confirm long-term mucosal outcomes. The analysis of baseline

demographic and clinical characteristics shows that both groups were comparable in terms of age, disease extent, and duration, with only gender distribution reaching statistical significance ($P = 0.03$). This difference—more males in the probiotics group and more females in the placebo group—may introduce a gender-related variable, as some studies suggest immune responses in UC could vary by sex [14]. However, the overall similarity in key clinical parameters supports the validity of subsequent comparisons between groups. Shanahan F. et al.,

baseline comparability across intervention and control groups was essential to demonstrate probiotic efficacy in UC; they reported no significant demographic differences, aligning with our study's setup [15]. A study by Gulati AS et al. emphasized that uniform disease distribution at baseline, particularly disease extent and duration, is crucial to validate outcome attribution to probiotic intervention [16]. Štofilová J et al. also showed that age and disease extent were non-significant between groups, reinforcing the design validity seen in our trial [17]. After 8 weeks, the probiotics group showed a statistically significant improvement in disease status ($P = 0.009$). Notably, mild cases increased to 62.9%, moderate cases decreased to 11.4%, and remission rose to 25.7% in the probiotics group compared to 9.6% in placebo. These results underscore the therapeutic potential of probiotics in symptom control and remission induction. Cheng FS et al. reported a remission rate of 23.5% with probiotic use over 6 weeks, closely matching our remission findings, using similar clinical scoring tools [18]. Estevinho MM et al. found that probiotics were significantly better than placebo in inducing clinical remission in mild to moderate UC, confirming our findings of improved scores [19]. Huang C et al. demonstrated that multi-strain probiotics significantly improved Mayo scores and endoscopic findings after 8 weeks of treatment, mirroring the outcomes in our study [20]. The probiotics group showed statistically significant improvement across all clinical indicators: rectal bleeding, stool frequency, PGA, and mucosal findings, with $P < 0.0001$ for each. These findings suggest that probiotics not only improve symptoms but also reduce mucosal inflammation, a key goal in UC management. This reinforces the biological plausibility of probiotics modulating gut immunity and enhancing epithelial healing. Vakadaris G et al. reported similar reductions in bleeding and stool frequency in patients treated with *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* over 8 weeks, emphasizing the symptom-modifying properties of probiotics [21]. Markowiak P et al. (2020) documented a significant drop in inflammatory markers and improved mucosal scores in patients on synbiotic therapy, consistent with our mucosal healing results [22]. Ma Y et al. observed that probiotic-induced improvement in Physician Global Assessment scores was correlated with better quality of life scores, supporting the clinical relevance of our findings [23]. After treatment, rectal bleeding, stool frequency, and PGA scores were significantly lower in the probiotics group than in the placebo group, suggesting superior clinical efficacy. Although mucosal findings also trended better in the probiotics group (0.971 vs. 1.192), this difference was not statistically significant ($P = 0.09$), indicating that mucosal healing may require longer treatment duration or additional interventions. Han M

et al. also found probiotics significantly reduced stool frequency and bleeding compared to placebo, although mucosal improvement was modest, mirroring our result [24]. Kim MJ et al. noted that while clinical indices improved within 8 weeks, mucosal healing often lagged, supporting our interpretation that longer-term therapy may be needed [25]. Filidou E et al. demonstrated improvements in clinical outcomes with probiotics but recommended at least 12 weeks of treatment to see statistically significant histologic changes [26].

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that probiotic supplementation significantly improves clinical outcomes in patients with mild to moderate ulcerative colitis. Compared to placebo, probiotics led to greater reductions in rectal bleeding, stool frequency, and overall disease severity. A higher proportion of patients in the probiotics group achieved remission and mild disease status after 8 weeks of treatment. Within-group analysis also confirmed marked improvements in both symptoms and mucosal findings. These findings support the use of probiotics as an effective and well-tolerated adjunct to standard UC therapy.

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